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National Centre for Energy and Environment,
Energy Commission of Nigeria, University of Benin:
ISSN 2504-9593

Int. J. Renew. Energ & Environ Vol.3(2), pp 172- 189(2025)

WEIGHT OPTIMIZATION OF 3D PRINTED PLATE SKID LANDING GEAR FOR IMPROVED ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN FIXED WING UAVS

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ABSTRACT

This study details the structural optimization of a 3D-printed plate skid landing gear for fixed-wing unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to improve flight endurance and operational efficiency through weight reduction. The study integrated Topology Optimization (TO) with Additive Manufacturing (AM) techniques, using ANSYS Mechanical for Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulations to ensure structural integrity under both ground and aerodynamic loads. Topology Optimization revealed the minimal load-bearing regions, enabling targeted material removal while maintaining the exterior airfoil shape. The optimized design achieved a 9.6% weight reduction (from 88.28 g to 79.80 g). Structural performance remained robust: maximum equivalent stress increased negligibly (0.84%), and reduction in factor of safety was minimal. Successfully fabricated using Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), the new design also reduced production time by 1.89%. This research confirms that the synergy of TO and AM is a viable pathway for developing lighter, more energy-efficient UAV components, and this methodology can be extended to optimize other UAV parts and aerospace structures.

Keywords: *Topology optimization, Additive manufacturing, UAV landing gear, Weight reduction, Finite element analysis, Fluid-structure interaction, Fused deposition modeling*

1. Introduction

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have become essential tools across diverse industries owing to their versatility, cost-effectiveness, and ability to perform tasks that are difficult or hazardous for manned aircraft. Initially developed for military use, UAVs are now widely adopted in civilian applications such as search and rescue missions and coastal surveillance, where long-range, high-endurance platforms are particularly valuable (Pecho et al., 2019). While UAV designs are tailored to specific mission profiles, endurance remains a critical parameter, as longer flight times reduce the need for frequent refueling or battery recharging, thereby enhancing operational efficiency (Goh et al., 2016). A key contributor to UAV endurance is weight minimization, which directly influences flight

range and efficiency. Landing gear is a fundamental but often challenging component to optimize, as it must ensure structural integrity during takeoff, landing, and ground operations while balancing aerodynamic performance and weight (Ferro et al., 2015). Conventional manufacturing methods can limit the design freedom necessary to achieve these optimizations due to constraints on geometry and material distribution.

Recent advances in structural optimization techniques, particularly topology optimization (TO), have provided powerful tools for achieving highly material-efficient designs. TO leverages finite element analysis and mathematical optimization algorithms to determine the optimal material distribution

within a given design space, retaining only what is structurally necessary (Walker and Liu, 2015). This approach is especially valuable in aerospace engineering, where reducing weight without compromising strength or stiffness is paramount. Simultaneously, additive manufacturing (AM), particularly Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), has revolutionized the production of complex, lightweight components. Unlike traditional subtractive methods, AM enables the fabrication of intricate geometries without the constraints of machining or molding, making it an attractive and cost-effective solution for producing optimized aerospace structures (Klippstein et al., 2019). The integration of TO and AM allows for the realization of advanced designs that reduce weight while maintaining or even improving structural performance and aerodynamic properties (Miguel, 2019). Despite these advancements, there remains limited research on applying TO and AM in the design of UAV landing gear, particularly for achieving weight reduction without compromising structural integrity or aerodynamic efficiency. Traditional landing gear designs for UAVs often neglect the potential of these technologies, resulting in heavier and less efficient components.

This study addresses this gap by focusing on the structural optimization of a 3D-printed plate skid landing gear for fixed-wing UAVs. Using topology optimization techniques integrated with FDM-friendly design constraints, the goal is to reduce weight while maintaining structural integrity, aerodynamic smoothness, and cost-effectiveness. The approach involves CAD modeling in SolidWorks, static structural and one-way fluid-structure interaction (FSI) analyses in ANSYS, and topology density optimization to identify non-critical material regions. The optimized design is then refined for FDM additive manufacturing and successfully 3D printed, demonstrating the feasibility of translating the computationally optimized

design into a physical, manufacturable component. By demonstrating this process, the study aims to contribute to the development of lighter, more efficient UAV components, enable cost-effective manufacturing of complex designs, promote sustainable material usage, and expand the application of advanced optimization and manufacturing techniques in aerospace engineering.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Structural and Topology Optimization

Structural optimization aims to improve performance while minimizing weight and material use. Among its forms; size, shape, and topology optimization (TO), TO is particularly valuable for aerospace applications due to its ability to redistribute material for maximum efficiency (Xue-Ping et al., 2016). Historically, TO evolved from early truss analyses (Maxwell, 1854; Michell, 1904) to continuum methods such as the ground structure method (Dorn et al., 1964) and homogenization (Bendsoe et al., 1988). Modern algorithms include SIMP (Rozvany, 2009) and BESO (Querin et al., 2007), both widely used for their balance of efficiency and simplicity.

TO typically seeks to minimize compliance (maximize stiffness) under volume constraints by assigning density variables in finite element models. Advances in optimization algorithms and computing power have expanded its use across industries, including aerospace, automotive, and marine engineering.

2.2. Additive Manufacturing (AM)

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is defined as the layer-by-layer fabrication of objects from 3D models (ASTM F42, 2012). Originally developed for rapid prototyping in the 1980s, AM technologies such as Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), Stereolithography (SLA), and Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) now enable production of complex, functional

components (Goh et al., 2015; Wohlers et al., 2022). AM offers advantages including design freedom, reduced material waste, and lower production costs for low-volume or customized parts. However, limitations such as anisotropic mechanical properties and the need for support materials can affect structural performance (Ahn et al., 2013).

2.3. Integrating Topology Optimization and AM

The synergy between TO and AM removes traditional manufacturing constraints, allowing fabrication of highly optimized, weight-efficient geometries (Gardan, 2015). In aerospace applications, this integration is especially valuable for producing lightweight components while maintaining structural integrity. Studies show TO-driven designs can be manufactured cost-effectively via AM, improving both performance and production flexibility (James et al., 2014).

2.4. Applications in UAV Design: Case Studies

Recent developments illustrate the transformative impact of AM and TO on UAV design and manufacturing:

- a. **AMRC Design and Prototyping Group (2014)**: Produced an ABS plastic UAV airframe entirely via FDM, reducing production time from over 120 hours to under 24, demonstrating FDM's suitability for small, lightweight UAVs.
- b. **RecordRotor (2015)**: A multi-rotor UAV developed by Altair Engineering and Politecnico di Torino using TO and AM, combining carbon fiber and 7075 alloy with AM polymer components to achieve high performance.
- c. **SULSA UAV (2011)**: The first fully 3D-printed aircraft using laser sintering, featuring snap-fit assembly and rapid production, weighing only 3 kg with a 1.2 m wingspan.
- d. **Aurora Flight Sciences UAV**: Developed in partnership with Stratasys Ltd, featuring

80% 3D-printed components, including nylon fuselage and metal exhaust duct, achieving speeds up to 241 km/h.

- e. **Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT)**: Applied AM and TO to create a lightweight, optimized UAV wing structure using aluminum alloys, reducing compliance while meeting relaxed airworthiness constraints (Walker et al., 2015).

These cases illustrate how integrating TO and AM enables faster, cheaper, and more efficient UAV production with improved design flexibility and performance.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Materials

This study relied on a combination of advanced software for design and simulation, as well as reliable hardware for prototyping through additive manufacturing.

a. Software

The primary design work was carried out in SolidWorks 2023, a parametric CAD tool well suited for complex mechanical geometries. The landing gear was modeled to incorporate an outer airfoil-like shape for minimal drag while preserving sufficient internal volume for load-bearing. SolidWorks enabled detailed modeling with export to formats compatible with simulation workflows.

Simulation and analysis were conducted using ANSYS Workbench 2024 R2, providing an integrated environment for linking CAD data with advanced analysis. Within this suite, ANSYS Mechanical was employed for structural analysis and topology optimization, using ABS plastic properties with density of 1030 kg/m³ and a tensile yield strength of 27.4 MPa. ANSYS Fluent was used to simulate aerodynamic loading, modeling airflow at 50 m/s to generate realistic pressure distributions over the landing gear surface. The one-way fluid-structure interaction (FSI)

capability in Workbench facilitated transferring aerodynamic pressures from Fluent to Mechanical for structural evaluation.

b. Hardware

Prototyping of the designs was performed using a BambuLab P1P FDM 3D printer. This machine, known for its precision and multicolor capability, offers a build volume of

$256 \times 256 \times 256$ mm with layer resolutions as fine as 0.1 mm. For this study, Bambu PLA Basic filament in cream color was used to fabricate scaled versions of the landing gear, demonstrating the feasibility of manufacturing the optimized design without supports thanks to careful internal geometry refinement.

Figure 1: BambuLab P1P Multicolor Desktop FDM Printer

3.2. Methodology

I. CAD Modeling

The landing gear was modeled in SolidWorks with an airfoil-shaped exterior to minimize

drag. The design was exported in .IGES format and imported into ANSYS Workbench.

Figure 2: Geometric model of landing gear in Solidworks

II. Static Structural Analysis

A static structural module simulated landing gear performance under the UAV's ground weight. ABS plastic was selected as the material with properties including:

- Density: 1030 kg/m³
- Yield Strength: 27.4 MPa

The simulation was carried out using a detailed 5 mm mesh and downward force of 50 N applied in the Y-axis to represent UAV weight.

Figure 3: Meshed model

Figure 4: Applied load boundary condition

III. Topology Optimization (Ground Scenario)

Following the static analysis, topology optimization was conducted in ANSYS Mechanical to identify low-stress regions suitable for material removal while preserving structural integrity.

IV. Aerodynamic Simulation in Fluent

Using ANSYS Fluent, a CFD simulation at 50 m/s airspeed calculated drag forces on the landing gear during flight. These pressure loads were exported for structural analysis

Figure 5: Imported aerodynamic pressure distribution on the landing gear model

V. One-Way Fluid-Structure Interaction

Aerodynamic loads from Fluent were applied to the structural model in ANSYS Mechanical to evaluate stress, deformation, and factor of

safety under in-flight conditions. Topology optimization was repeated for aerodynamic loading.

Figure 6: Workflow for one-way fluid-structure interaction with structural optimization

VI. Comparative Optimization

The results of the static structural analysis and aerodynamic optimization were compared to identify common areas where material had been removed. These regions were considered non-critical for both load-bearing be it by the weight of the UAV or the aerodynamic drag experienced during flight, indicating that material could be safely removed in these areas without affecting the overall functionality or structural integrity of the landing gear.

VII. Final Design Refinement

Using the insights from the optimization processes, material was removed from the internal sections of the landing gear design in SolidWorks. Care was taken to preserve

the outer airfoil shape to ensure that aerodynamic performance remained unaffected. The updated model represented the optimized design, balancing weight reduction with structural and aerodynamic requirements.

VIII. Validation of the Optimized Model

The optimized landing gear design was re-imported into ANSYS for validation. The validation process focused on static structural analysis to compare the performance metrics such as FOS, stress, and deformation of the optimized model against the original. Validation of the aerodynamic module was deemed unnecessary as the outer geometry was unaltered during optimization.

IX. Additive Manufacturing of Landing Gear Models

The optimized and standard designs were scaled to 70% of their original size to fit the BambuLab P1P printer bed. Slicing was performed in Bambu Studio using the following profile:

- **Layer height:** 0.2 mm
- **Infill:** 50% density, triangle pattern
- **Support threshold:** 30°
- **Filament:** Bambu PLA Basic, cream color

Triangular infills were chosen for their consistent layer deposition and strong strength-to-weight ratio. Honeycomb infills

were avoided due to common print defects from alternating wall passes (Klippstein et al., 2018).

Printed models included both sectioned and full versions to visually confirm the feasibility of manufacturing the optimized internal geometry. Physical stress testing was not conducted, as the scope was limited to computational validation and manufacturability demonstration.

4. Results

A. Structural Analysis of Landing Gear Based on UAV Weight

Minimum[Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
5851.8	1.3788e+007	1.9984e+006

Figure 7: Contours of Equivalent Stress on the landing gear

Total Deformation

Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
0.	5.4587e-002	2.2589e-002

Figure 8: Contours of Total deformation of the landing gear

Safety Factor

Minimum	Maximum	Average
1.9902	15.	12.447

Figure 9: Contours of Factor of Safety of the Landing Gear

B. Structural Analysis of Landing Gear Based on Aerodynamic Load

Equivalent Stress

Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
0.	12705	2044.

Figure 10: Contours of equivalent stress from imported aerodynamic pressure load

Total Deformation

Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
0.	2.3947e-007	5.5389e-008

Figure 11: Contours of total deformation from imported aerodynamic pressure load

Safety Factor

Minimum	Maximum	Average
15.	15.	15.

C. Structural Optimization; Comparison of Topology Densities for Weight and Aerodynamic Load

a. Topology Optimization of Landing Gear when Subject to UAV Weight

Figure 12: Topology density of landing gear based on UAV weight

b. Topology Optimization of Landing Gear when Subject to Aerodynamic Loads

Figure 13: Topology density of landing gear based on Aerodynamic load

D. Geometry Refinement; Creation of Optimized Landing Gear Model

Figure 14: Refined geometry with material removed in areas contributing least to load bearing

Figure 15: Section view of standard model

Figure 16: Section view of optimized model showing areas of material removal

E. Validation of Optimized Model

Equivalent Stress

Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
12123	1.3904e+007	2.0606e+006

Figure 17: Contours of equivalent stress for optimized landing gear model

Total Deformation

Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
0.	5.2699e-002	2.0986e-002

Figure 18: Contours of total deformation for optimized landing gear model

Safety Factor

Minimum	Maximum	Average
1.9735	15.	12.374

Figure 19: Contours of factor of safety for optimized landing gear model

F. Additive Manufacturing of Landing Gear Models:

Model Estimation

Standard Landing Gear Model:

- **Size:** 192.319 x 7.00532 x 246.939 mm

- **Volume:** 102227mm²
- **Total Filament:** 88.28g and 29.13m
- **Total Print Time:** 3 hours and 31 minutes

Figure 20: Print profile of standard landing gear model

Figure 21: Print profile showing triangular infills

Optimized Landing Gear Model:

- **Size:** 192.319 x 7.00532 x 240.056 mm
- **Volume:** 78,895.4mm²

- **Total Filament:** 75.96g and 25.07m
- **Total Print Time:** 3 hours and 23 minutes

Figure 22: Print profile of optimized landing gear model

Figure 23: Print profile of optimized landing gear showing infills

Figure 24: Final 3D printed model on build plate

5. Discussion

This section explores the interpretation and implications of the results obtained from the structural and aerodynamic analyses of the plate skid landing gear. The discussion focuses on the dual considerations of ground weight support and aerodynamic drag forces experienced during flight, providing insights into the design's structural efficiency and the impact of optimization.

Through topology optimization, areas of the landing gear contributing minimally to load bearing were identified. The results revealed that the rear curved section of the landing gear (rear arc) consistently demonstrated low load-bearing contributions under both static structural and aerodynamic load conditions. This finding informed the material removal process, where Solidworks was employed to refine the internal structure of the landing gear while maintaining the outer airfoil shape to preserve aerodynamic integrity.

The optimized model was validated through a secondary static structural simulation in ANSYS, confirming its improved performance

metrics while retaining structural integrity. Additionally, the manufacturability of the optimized design was evaluated through 3D printing, with the printed models serving to demonstrate the feasibility of implementing the proposed modifications using additive manufacturing technology.

This discussion explores the broader implications of these findings, comparing the original and optimized designs in terms of stress distribution, deformation, factor of safety, and weight reduction. The interplay between structural efficiency and manufacturability is analyzed, with particular attention to how the results inform future UAV landing gear designs.

The comparison of the standard and optimized landing gear designs demonstrates the effectiveness of topology optimization and additive manufacturing in achieving weight reduction without compromising structural integrity or manufacturability, as can be seen in table 1 below;

Table 1: Comparative summary of key results for the Standard and Optimized Landing Gear designs.

Parameters	Standard Landing Gear	Optimized Landing Gear	% Change
Max Equivalent Stress (Pa)	1.3788×10^7	1.3904×10^7	0.84% Increase
Total Deformation (m)	5.4587×10^{-2}	5.2699×10^{-2}	3.46% Decrease
Minimum Factor of Safety	1.9902	1.9735	0.84% Decrease
Weight (kg)	8.828×10^{-2}	7.980×10^{-2}	9.6% Decrease
Production Time (min)	211	207	1.89% Decrease

The optimized landing gear achieved a weight reduction of 9.6%, decreasing from 88.28 g to 79.80 g. Even modest reductions like this are critical in UAV design, where lower weight improves energy efficiency, extends flight range, and reduces operating costs. This result confirms the optimization process successfully identified non-critical internal regions that could be removed without sacrificing load-bearing capability.

Structural performance metrics remained well within acceptable limits. The maximum equivalent stress of the optimized design increased only slightly by 0.84%, still well below the material's yield strength. This small rise reflects efficient stress redistribution in the streamlined structure. Similarly, the factor of safety saw a minor reduction of 0.84%, yet remained comfortably above the minimum safe threshold, demonstrating that the optimized design preserves operational safety despite reduced material usage.

From a manufacturing standpoint, production time decreased slightly by 1.89%, from 3 hours 31 minutes to 3 hours 27 minutes. Although modest, this reduction, combined with lower material use, suggests improved production efficiency and cost-effectiveness. It also supports sustainability goals by minimizing material waste and energy consumption during fabrication.

Overall, the results validate the approach of using topology optimization and additive manufacturing for UAV components. By

carefully identifying and removing minimal load-bearing parts, it is possible to achieve meaningful weight reductions while maintaining structural reliability and manufacturing feasibility. This approach sets a precedent for applying similar lightweighting strategies across other UAV components (like wingspan, horizontal and vertical tail plane) to enhance overall performance and efficiency.

6. Limitations and Recommendations

Despite the promising results achieved in this study, several limitations were encountered that highlight areas for future improvement.

A primary limitation was the necessity to scale down the landing gear model to 70% of its original size to fit the build volume of the desktop FDM printer. While this adjustment enabled successful fabrication for demonstration purposes, it reveals the constraints of current desktop additive manufacturing technologies in producing full-scale UAV components, particularly those with larger dimensions.

Another challenge emerged from the nature of the weight optimization process, which involves removing internal material to create voids. In practice, if the top of these voids remains closed in the CAD model, FDM printing software will often generate support material to fill these cavities. This unintended filling reduces the weight savings and negates some of the optimization's benefits, pointing to

a need for better design-for-manufacturing integration.

Future research should explore practical methods for managing open cavities during printing. For example, leaving the top of the landing gear open in the CAD model would allow for printing without internal support material. Post-print sealing techniques such as adhesive bonding, thermal fusion, or custom-fitted caps could then close these openings.

7. Conclusion

This study successfully demonstrated the potential of integrating topology optimization and additive manufacturing to improve the design of a plate skid landing gear for fixed-wing UAVs. By applying advanced simulation techniques in ANSYS and leveraging SolidWorks for design refinement, the project achieved a 9.6% reduction in weight without compromising structural integrity or aerodynamic performance.

Despite a slight increase in maximum stress and a minor reduction in the factor of safety, both remained well within acceptable limits, while total deformation actually decreased, indicating improved stiffness. The optimized design also preserved the essential airfoil-shaped exterior, ensuring that aerodynamic efficiency was maintained.

The results underscore the effectiveness of topology optimization in identifying minimal load-bearing parts for material removal and highlight the practicality of additive manufacturing, particularly FDM, in producing the resulting geometries. Together, these approaches enable more efficient, lightweight UAV components that can contribute to improved flight endurance and operational efficiency.

Future work should focus on refining topology optimization algorithms to better account for manufacturing constraints, testing printed components under real-world loading

conditions, and exploring advanced AM techniques such as metal printing or hybrid approaches. Such developments will further expand the potential of these technologies to produce high-performance, cost-effective UAV components.

Overall, this research demonstrates a promising pathway toward lighter, more efficient, and manufacturable UAV landing gear designs, paving the way for broader application of optimization and additive manufacturing in the aerospace industry.

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